

**METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF
THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

Rayimdjanova G.X.

doctoral student,
Ferghana State University

Annotation.

The article discusses in detail the changes in the economic system, which is digitalization. The main factors of the digital economy development are analyzed: Internet of Things, universal Internet, high communication, applications and services based on cloud technologies, big data analysis, automation, robotics, multi-channel or channel models of distribution of goods and services.

Keywords: digital economy, Internet of Things, high connectivity, cloud technologies, automation, robotics.

Introduction.

The Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis states that in order to further develop science in our country, educate our youth with deep knowledge, high spirituality and culture, continue the work begun on the formation of a competitive economy and raising it to a new, modern level, 2020 is called the Year of Science, Education and Digital Economy. It is necessary to carry out large-scale work on the priority development and reform of the areas identified in 2020. In particular, this year it is necessary to increase the coverage of preschool children with preschool education to 60 percent. This year, about 1.8 trillion rubles will be allocated from the budget for these purposes.soums.

Materials and methods. Digitalization is the most dynamic process that will bring significant changes to the economic system. The main factors in the development of the digital economy are: the Internet of Things, universal Internet, high communication, applications and services based on cloud technologies, big data

analysis, automation, robotics, multi-channel or channel models for the distribution of goods and services.

The changes that are taking place are radical, they introduce other values and behaviors in the market of firms, their customers and consumers.

Results. Therefore, it is important for economic scientists and active politicians in developing countries to understand that today we need to focus on the institutional environment, and not on economic reforms. Secondly, in order to meet the requirements of the digital economy, it is necessary to modernize the structures of digital thinking in order to reduce high-level opportunism by including them in the standard values of business practice.

To do this, the methodological foundations of the economy should be freed from the old approach to the sustainable growth of consumer goods, that is, the function of maximizing useful services. Over time, the crisis of economic theory will be overcome, and new concepts close to the digital economy will appear.

In 2011, German Professor of Physics and Chairman of SAP G.Kagerman presented the concept of the "fourth industrial revolution". It consists of industry, automotive and logistics.

Representatives of Western schools are studying ways to implement it. In particular, living in an unnatural social environment for institutions. In conclusion, an institutional project should be calculated in terms of transaction costs if its flexibility in the economic environment is low.

Another area of research is the assessment of methodological individualism. This is the basis of the liberal model of the economy. It is based on the idea of freedom of entrepreneurship and the principle of maximizing profits through currency exchange operations in a market economy.

Western individualism should be reasonable and develop methods to assess and minimize potential risks before any indicator. The new institutional economic theory introduces the concept of limited rationalization. That is, decision makers cannot determine transaction costs to obtain information. Because people are prone to

opportunism, contractors are not always reliable. Therefore, opportunistic deals should be protected before they are concluded, and the accumulated experience should be used later.

Methodological individualism in modern institutionalism is the movement of a purposeful person who responds to the institutions of the economic system by directing and limiting his actions. But this principle is not applied in new economic programs. In particular, it creates a multi-institutional environment for States with many cultural traditions and different religious beliefs.

Discussion. The second one includes: religious traditions of Orthodoxy, Islam, Buddhism, Confucianism, the best examples of European and Eastern cultures; about fictitious legal relations of economic behavior; can be based on new standards of behavior using the global infosphere and IT.

In all countries, reforms based on methodological individuality have not led to the expected results. With an increase in living standards and consumer demand at home, people's behavior began to change, the advantages of large-scale production disappeared, and interest in standardized products decreased.

Consumers began to pay for the diversity and differentiation of goods. Price competition in the developing middle class has led to quality indicators. Entrepreneurship has acquired network structures managed from international centers. According to the models of monetarism and Keynesianism, this should lead to the development of an industrial small business that meets demand and is adapted to continuous economic growth.

But in many countries this is not the case. Competition is underdeveloped, small businesses are focused on speculative behavior, and the level of opportunism can be high. In order to implement the fourth industrial revolution, it is necessary to use the individual characteristics of citizens in economic policy.

Recently, firms have created communities (thiamism) in which the role of the individual in decision-making is reduced, and opportunistic behavior is limited. The crowd principle (crowdism) is often applied when a crowded economy is formed in a

socio-economic environment, and social networks are organized by a special administrator.

But, for example, Russian individualism is based on limited rationalization, characterized by a high degree of opportunism and the crowd. Economic interests in this country can be included in one of four models of the correlation of moral and economic interests. Therefore, the economic development program of the new Russia can be called moral institutionalism.

Currently, mining and online exchanges are developing in Russia, which leads to an increase in fraud. Therefore, it is necessary to study the problems associated with bitcoin and other digital tokens in order to prevent crime in this area. Since fraud is associated with opportunistic behavior, its social consequences are widespread.

Therefore, the material consequences are the damage caused to property. This is a social manifestation of the growth of psychological tension and anxiety in society. It also reduces public confidence in financial institutions and the state, which leads to disruption of public life. The future of the digital economy is not entirely clear yet, but a cultural revolution is about to take place, which needs to be directed in the right direction. At the same time, it is necessary to study business processes in Western Europe.

Thus, the EU initiative "Industry" is aimed at developing the concepts of the industrial Internet of Things, intelligent industry, smart enterprises, flexible factories, advanced manufacturing. Among the national enterprises, the development of factories of the future in Italy, the British initiative of the newest industrial production centers, and the French concept of future industry stand out.

Poland is the fastest growing country in the field of digitalization. Over the past decade, key elements of the ICT infrastructure (telecommunication networks, platforms, applications, databases) have been created in the country.

The Polish government adopted a development strategy when the concept of a service-oriented state became a key area of public awareness: the formation of a digital government that serves citizens and businesses, the safe use of the Internet and utilities,

modern telecommunications and technological infrastructure, as well as digital competencies, public opinion, the formation of customs, rules of etiquette and values.

Today, there is competition in the European market using traditional business models and new business models that combine different industries and offer a wide range of products and services that they deliver to their customers using electronic logistics. Firms that have revolutionized business organization use a combination of all of the above models. This includes Google Inc., which recently acquired companies that produce robots, autonomous cars and airplanes.

In the coming years, there will be three trends in the digital revolution: the relationship between people and machines, the intellectualization of machines for work, and the evolution of interpersonal relationships.

As a result, consistent measures have been taken recently to develop the digital economy, and e-commerce systems for the exchange of electronic documents and services for individuals and legal entities have been gradually introduced in government agencies and other organizations. At the same time, an analysis of the real situation on the ground shows that the implemented program documents are fragmented due to the lack of a single information technology platform that provides integration into a centralized data system. In order to create conditions for the rapid development of the digital economy, further improvement of the public administration system, expansion of access to it, and the use of modern infrastructure:

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for further modernization of digital infrastructure for the development of the digital economy" dated 21.11.2018 UP-4022 was decided. The resolution states that for information: The National Agency for Project Management under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the Agency) is the competent authority in the field of implementation and development of the digital economy.

Conclusion. One of the main tasks to attract and consolidate investors' funds for the implementation of projects in the digital economy, including the introduction of

blockchain technologies in public-private partnership, is the creation of the Digital Economy Support Fund Digital Trust.

The document also includes a proposal from the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications, the State Committee for Privatization and Competition Development, the Agency, the Ministry of Economy, the Ministry of Finance, the State Tax Committee to transfer to the Fund a 100% state share in the authorized capital of Universal Mobile Systems.

Literature.

1. Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. Tashkent, 2017, December 26
2. Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. Tashkent, 2018, December 29
3. Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. Tashkent, 2020, January 24.
4. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures for the introduction of the digital economy, electronic government and information systems in the public administration of the Republic of Uzbekistan". 13.12.2018, UP-5598.
5. Khalmatjanova, G. D., Yuldasheva, G. A., Rayimdjanova, G. K. (2022). Features of Criteria of Profitability of Cotton–Textile Cluster. In E. G. Popkova, & B. S. Sergi (Eds.), *Sustainable Agriculture*. Singapore: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1125-5_12
6. Halmatjanova G.D. Locomotive of the agricultural sector of the economy. Zh.: Education and science in Russia and abroad. : Moscow. №3, 2020.
7. Halmatjanova, G. D., & Rayimdzhanova, G. H. (2020). The cluster mechanism is a way to modernize the textile industry of Uzbekistan. Interuniversity Scientific Congress:"Higher school: scientific research". SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH, 28.

8. Khalmatjanova, G. D. (2020). Mechanisms of formation of agricultural clusters in the economy of Uzbekistan. *ACADEMIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 10(12), 847-852.

9. Halmatjanova, G. D. (2021). THE NEED FOR THE FORMATION AND INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AN AGRICULTURAL CLUSTER IN UZBEKISTAN. *Scientific progress*, 2(3), 179-186.

10. Halmatjanova, G. (2020). CLUSTERS ARE A FACTOR DETERMINING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Editorial Board: PM Pershukevich, Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 319.11.

11 Halmatjanova, G. J. (2020). The locomotive of the agricultural sectorz. *Education and Science in Russia and abroad*, (3), 55-56.

12. Halmatjanova, G. D. (2019). Modernization and diversification is a priority task of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Education and Science in Russia and Abroad*, (16), 373-377.

13. Halmatjanova, G. D., & Bahramov, A. H. (2020). ENSURING SUSTAINABLE AND BALANCED DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONS. In *MINTAKA IKTISODIETINI INVESTYALASHNING MOLİYAVIY-ҲУКУКИЙ VA INNOVATION ZHIATLARI* (pp. 219-225).

14. Halmatjanova, G. D., & Mannopova, M. S. (2020). THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE WORLD ECONOMY. In *MINTAKA IKTISODIETINI INVESTYALASHNING MOLİYAVIY-ҲУКУКИЙ VA INNOVATION ZHIATLARI* (pp. 238-244).

15. Halmatjanova, G. D., & Madaminov, Zh. (2008). INVESTMENTS ARE A STIMULATOR OF SUSTAINABLE GROWTH. *Questions of Economic Sciences*, (4), 80-81.

16. Halmatjanova, G. D. (2021). DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.